

Gatekeeping and Social Closure in Academic Careers

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Who becomes an elite member and why? As we know from the sociology of elites that elite status corresponds to societal status, power, and social background, the question arises to what extent scientific elite status is based on scientific performance and excellence or which other ascriptions constitute status advancement. Sociological studies on recruitment in elite circles point to the importance of cultural matching, which usually describes a fit between recruiters and candidates based on high culture (Friedman/Laurison 2020, Hartmann 2000, Rivera 2015). For science, however, there are hardly any studies so far that examine the "getting on" (Friedman/Laurison 2020: 9) within scientific careers regarding social background.

The study "The Social Order of the Field" (Keil 2020, 2023) addresses social closure through gatekeeping by studying gatekeepers' performance ascription and promotion and recruitment practices in the German social sciences. The qualitative grounded theory study is based on interview and academic cv data with postdocs and professors from sociology, political science, and education. The field and habitus theoretical framework (Bourdieu 1975, 1990) of the study places a focus on scientific practices of distinction, positioning within the field of the social sciences, and strategies of career advancement by these gatekeepers.

My study shows that recruitment practices and notions of performance vary across the field of the social sciences. As scientific practices are connected to subfield logics and distinctions, social closure is potentially produced through these field-specific logics and their adaptation and embodiment. Especially the idea of what constitutes good science at its core – be it enlightening society, providing expertise, or solving concrete problems – varies by the epistemic position within the field. Based on their patterns of perception, thinking, and evaluation,

the gatekeepers perceive questions and arguments of younger scientists as more or less relevant, original, and innovative. Differentiating the field of the social sciences based on the practical logic of scientific practices and academic positioning, three principles of research in the social sciences can be worked out: research as enlightenment at the autonomous pole of the field, research as expertise in the middle between autonomous and heteronomous pole and research as a societal mission at the heteronomous pole.

Social science at the autonomous pole focuses on theories and foundational research up to political-philosophical questions. In this field segment, methods, methodologies, and theories themselves become the object of research and are not only used as tools for research. The academic subject and the scientific community form the reference point of research and autonomous social science and thus tends to be self-referential. The promotion and labour relations are often based on informal recruitment situations and form a barter deal: the mentor introduces the mentees to their network and provides them with employment and funding until they are scientifically established enough to take up a professorship of their own (patronage). In return, the mentees follow the research agenda of the mentor and continue it, which contributes to the reputation and symbolic capital of the mentor. Thus, habitual matching is particularly important for long-term support and work relationships. Since habitual fit is measured by one's dispositions, the gatekeepers, most of whom come from the upper classes, tend to recruit their kind. In addition to institutional opportunities, gatekeeping in this field segment also strongly influences epistemic developments, since the funding relationships serve to enhance the reputation of schools of thought and theoretical traditions.

In the middle field segment between the poles of heteronomy and autonomy, the social sciences show a stronger specialisation and object orientation. Research topics and methodological and theoretical approaches often form a unit in the sense of a (specialised) research program, and new and unorthodox research topics as well as “the studies” (higher education studies, gender studies, etc.) can be located here. The reference point of research is not only the academic field, but research also serves expertise in other fields by contributing to socio-political and scientific-analytical decision-making and problem-solving processes in the respective field of practice. But it also provides expertise within the academy by establishing and advancing concrete professional discourses and subdisciplines. Interestingly, the special nature of new, as yet little-established research topics seems to correlate with precarious, freelance forms of academic labour. These labour relations demand not only an active mode of managing one’s career but also a high degree of entrepreneurship. The risk of social closure arises, on the one hand, for risk-averse social scientists who do not have economic reserves or safety nets that enable spin-offs and precarious employment. On the other hand, establishing new topics, even those that run counter to the mainstream requires a sovereign habitus that knows the various subfields and how to navigate within them and “sell” their topic. Here, the development of social capital, including non-scientific actors, and risk-affine entrepreneurship is more relevant than a habitual-cultural fit with individual persons (gatekeepers).

At the heteronomous pole, social science is more strongly orientated towards application. Here, science serves to solve major societal problems and crosses disciplinary boundaries to do so. Due to the increase in non-scientific influences on research, large-scale interdisciplinary research projects and networks, financed by politics or industry, can also be identified here. Since the reference point of science is not only within, but above all outside of the (national) scientific field, both the range of collaborations and the international orientation are greater. Intra-disciplinary debates may even be dismissed as irrelevant and a game of distinction, while the quality of science is measured by its ability to solve concrete problems. The higher fluctuation

of staff and assessment tasks for job interviews makes recruitment processes and performance requirements more transparent than at the autonomous pole. As the selection is project-specific rather than mentor-specific, educational investments from early on as well as precarity managing and flexible, career-oriented strategies backed up by economic capital pay off here. The more interdisciplinary and internationally oriented research demands a corresponding profile from younger scientists. Thus, objective cultural capital, symbols of excellence such as prizes and grants, and a coherent profile and career are the more important as employment is not based on promotion relationships built on trust and loyalty.

The study shows that subtle distinctions within scientific practices and notions of performance in the (sub) fields of the social sciences function as symbolic boundaries and can manifest into real social boundaries in the case of funding and recruitment decisions.

References

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